

Analysis of the Communicative Strategies and Public Reception of Satirical Messages of *Makarantar Malam Mai Dalla Dalla* on COVID-19

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Abstract

This study investigated the communicative strategies and societal impact of *Makarantar Mallam Mai Dalla-Dalla*, a grassroots satirical media initiative in Northern Nigeria that gained prominence during the COVID-19 pandemic. Drawing on Ervin Goffman's Framing Theory, the research explored how the presenters used satire—grounded in the Hausa tradition of *Malanta* to reframe official public health narratives and amplify alternative interpretations aligned with local socio-cultural realities. Using a qualitative approach, in-depth interviews with the two (2) principal presenters, popularly known as *Mallam Mai Dalla-Dalla* and *Majabaki*, were conducted and thematically analysed. The findings reveal that the Dalla-Dalla presenters employed culturally embedded humour, local idioms, and vernacular linguistic innovations to rearticulate the pandemic as an elite or political construct, thereby challenging institutional messaging. Their performances addressed public scepticism, economic marginalisation and political discontent while simultaneously educating and engaging grassroots audiences. The study concluded that satire, when anchored in culturally resonant formats and disseminated through digital platforms, can serve as a powerful tool for public health communication, social critique, and civic participation. It recommended for greater institutional recognition of indigenous communicators, policy support for grassroots media and further research into the strategic integration of localised satire into formal health communication frameworks.

Keywords: COVID-19, Satire, Health Communication, *Dalla-Dalla*, Framing Theory, Nigeria, *Malanta*

Introduction